

Statistical review of *Remdesivir for 5 or 10 Days in Patients with Severe Covid-19*

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Kerry Hood, PhD - Professor of Trials, Centre for Trials Research, Cardiff University.

Jack Wilkinson, PhD - Research Fellow, Centre for Biostatistics, Manchester Academic Health Science Centre, University of Manchester.

The following review has been prepared in collaboration with members of the MRC-NIHR Trials Methodology Research Partnership¹. The reviewers named above, and other, unnamed discussants of the paper, are all qualified statisticians with experience in clinical trials. Our objective is to provide a rapid review of publications, preprints and protocols from clinical trials of COVID-19 treatments, independent of journal specific review processes. We aim to provide timely, constructive, focused, clear advice aimed at improving both the research outputs under review, as well as future studies. Given our collective expertise (clinical trial statistics) our reviews focus on the designs of the trials and other statistical content (methods, presentation and accuracy of results, inferences). This review reflects the expert opinions of the named authors, and does not imply endorsement by the MRC-NIHR Trials Methodology Research Partnership, its wider membership, or any other organisation.

Here we review *Remdesivir for 5 or 10 Days in Patients with Severe Covid-19*, by Goldman *et al*². The full text was published on May 27th in The New England Journal of Medicine, and is available at <https://www.nejm.org/doi/full/10.1056/NEJMoa2015301>.

Overall, this was an apparently well conducted trial comparing two doses of remdesivir in COVID-19. However, the trial's value is diminished by the lack of comparison to the standard-of-care, and its failure to use a non-inferiority to compare the different doses.

Study Summary

The paper describes a two-arm randomised controlled trial planned in 400 participants with severe COVID-19. The study was conducted between March 6th and March 26th, 2020. Participants were randomised in a 1:1 ratio to receive remdesivir for 5 or 10 days (200mg on day 1, 100mg on each day subsequently). A change was made to the primary outcome on March 15th, before results were available, from normalisation of temperature by day 14, to clinical status measured on a 7-point ordinal scale at day 14 (ranging from *death (1)* to *hospital discharge (7)*). Secondary outcomes included adverse events that occurred on or after the first dose of remdesivir for up to 30 days after the last dose; the time to clinical improvement (defined as an improvement of at least 2 points from baseline on the 7-point ordinal scale); the time to recovery (defined by the National Institute of Allergy and Infectious Diseases as an improvement from a baseline score of 2 to 5 to a score of 6 or 7); the time to modified recovery (defined as an improvement from a baseline score of 2 to 4 to a score of 5 to 7 or from a score of 5 to a score of 6 or 7); and death from any cause by 14 days post-randomisation.

A total of 400 participants were recruited; 397 initiated treatment and were included in the analysis. While 65% of the participants in the 5-day arm improved by at least 2 points on the ordinal scale, compared to 54% of those in the 10-day arm, a comparison of clinical status adjusted for baseline severity did not reveal a difference between the groups ($p = 0.14$). Although mortality (8% vs 11%) and median time to recovery (10 days vs 11 days) were lower, and the proportion of discharged patients was higher (60% vs 52%) in the 5 day group compared to the 10 day group, these differences were not inconsistent with the null hypothesis of no difference between the groups.

We sincerely thank the authors for their contribution to our collective understanding of COVID-19, and for their commitment to the timely dissemination of research results.

Major comments

The study was not designed to evaluate whether remdesivir was more effective than the standard-of-care.

Because no standard-of-care arm was included, the trial did not have assay sensitivity⁵. This means that the study was not able to say whether either regimen of remdesivir was superior to standard-of-care. Given that no evidence of a difference between the study arms was found, it is unclear whether both treatment regimens were similarly effective (compared to standard of care) or rather that both were ineffective.

Recommendations:*For future studies*

- Failure to include a standard-of-care arm leaves room for ambiguity in the interpretation of the result. It is recommended to include a suitable control arm, which allows the efficacy of any experimental treatment regimens to be assessed.

For the reader

- The reader should note that, in the absence of a standard-of-care control arm, the results are consistent with multiple interpretations. The study cannot address the question of how either regimen compares to standard of care.

A non-inferiority design might have been more appropriate for the authors' stated aims.

The authors motivated the study by noting that “A shorter course of treatment without a loss of efficacy could reduce hospital stays and potential adverse events and could extend the limited supply of remdesivir available during this pandemic.” Arguably this question would have been better addressed by a non-inferiority design (i.e. to show that one treatment is not appreciably worse than another), since failure to detect a difference between treatment groups when using superiority design does not automatically imply equivalence (i.e. “absence of evidence [of a difference] is not evidence of absence”³). Further, the absence of confidence intervals for the between-arm differences makes it difficult to assess non-inferiority *post-hoc*.

Recommendations:*For future studies*

- Where the goal is to demonstrate that a treatment is not materially inferior to an alternative, a superiority design is not recommended, because failure to detect a difference between groups does not constitute a demonstration of equivalence. Instead, the authors should have used a non-inferiority design, using a reasonable, pre-specified non-inferiority margin.

For the reader

- The reader should note that failure to detect a difference between treatment arms does not imply that the tested regimens are equivalent. Bespoke study designs can be used to test non-inferiority of one treatment compared to another. This involves pre-specifying a non-inferiority margin, and testing for evidence that the difference between treatments does not exceed this threshold.

Lack of blinding could have influenced the study's results.

This was an open-label study, meaning that patients and study personnel were aware of the treatment allocation. This can introduce bias if it results in material changes to behaviour that

are particular to the trial context. Further, any processes that might have been used to conceal treatment allocation were left undescribed in the paper. This makes it challenging to properly assess the importance of the baseline imbalance in clinical severity between the treatment arms - was it an artefact of chance, or were there biases in how patients were allocated, and perhaps subsequently treated or assessed?

Recommendations:

For future studies

- Where possible, trialists should attempt to blind participants and relevant personnel to treatment allocation.
- Carefully report the details of your randomisation and allocation concealment, following CONSORT⁴.

For this study

- It would be useful to present more details on the randomisation in relation to severity. There have been previous unblinded studies where subversion of the randomisation was shown to occur by staff who directed the sicker patients towards the treatment they believed worked better. Whilst the average number of patients per site is only 7, if one larger site was responsible for this imbalance it would warrant a sensitivity analysis with that site removed.

For the reader

- Lack of blinding can lead to differences in the way both participants and clinicians behave, compared to what would happen outside of the context of a clinical trial.

Minor comments

- It is usually a good idea to stratify the randomization by (and subsequently adjust for) study site in multi-centre trials, which was not done here.

- Although the primary outcome was changed, this appears to have been done before results were known, and the amended outcome was justified to be more clinically relevant.

- There were small numbers of post-randomisation exclusions, mainly due to mistakes in randomisation. Given the reported imbalance in baseline severity noted above, some more detail here would have been useful for the reader. Post randomisation exclusions are a violation of the intention to treat principle and therefore should be avoided where possible.

- Statistical tests for imbalances of baseline characteristics were performed, which is generally not recommended in a randomised trial⁴ since, provided that the randomisation was not subverted, the null hypothesis is known to be true (any differences between groups are attributable to chance).

- As a supplementary analysis, authors included a multivariable regression model to identify baseline predictors of outcome. The authors included several covariates in a regression model and reported those found to be associated. It is not clear that this approach yields useful or interpretable information, since the results cannot be given a causal interpretation and it does not follow that significantly associated variables are necessarily useful for prediction.

Open Data

No

Open Analysis Code

No

Pre-registered study design

<https://clinicaltrials.gov/ct2/show/NCT04292899>

PubPeer

There are currently no comments on the PubPeer page for the published version of this paper.

<https://pubpeer.com/publications/C3E4EF8A6DE0E326813B7C9B85312F>

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CONSORT CHECKLIST

To support the review, we completed the CONSORT checklist below. Material taken directly from the paper (or trial registry) is in *italics*. Our additional comments are in **bold**.

Title and abstract

1a Identification as a randomised trial in the title

No. (*Remdesivir for 5 or 10 Days in Patients with Severe Covid-19*)

1b Structured summary of trial design, methods, results, and conclusions.

Title: Identification of the study as randomised	No
Authors: Contact details for the corresponding author	Yes
Trial design: Description of the trial design (eg, parallel, cluster, non-inferiority)	Yes
Methods	
Participants: Eligibility criteria for participants and the settings where the data were collected	Yes
Interventions: Interventions intended for each group	Yes
Objective: Specific objective or hypothesis	Yes
Outcome: Clearly defined primary outcome for this report	Yes
Randomisation: How participants were allocated to interventions	Yes
Blinding (masking): Whether or not participants, care givers, and those assessing the outcomes were blinded to group assignment	Yes
Results	
Numbers randomised: Number of participants randomised to each group	Yes
Recruitment: Trial status	Yes
Numbers analysed: Number of participants analysed in each group	Yes
Outcome: For the primary outcome, a result for each group and the estimated effect size and its precision	Yes
Harms: Important adverse events or side-effects	Yes
Conclusions: General interpretation of the results	Yes
Trial registration: Registration number and name of trial register	Yes
Funding: Source of funding	Yes

Introduction

Background and objectives

2a Scientific background and explanation of rationale

See Introduction

2b Specific objectives or hypotheses

“...evaluating the efficacy and safety of treatment with remdesivir for 5 or 10 days in patients with severe Covid-19 disease” **[introduction]**

Methods

Trial design

3a Description of trial design (such as parallel, factorial) including allocation ratio

“Patients were randomly assigned in a 1:1 ratio to receive intravenous treatment with remdesivir for 5 days or 10 days. The randomization was not stratified” **[Trial design and oversight]**

3b Important changes to methods after trial commencement (such as eligibility criteria), with reasons

“The protocol was amended on March 15, 2020, after the beginning of enrollment but before any results were available. The lower age limit for eligibility was reduced from 18 years to 12 years, and a requirement for an axillary temperature of at least 36.6°C at screening was eliminated. In addition, one of the primary efficacy assessments — the proportions of patients with normalization of temperature at day 14 — was changed to assessment of clinical status on a 7-point ordinal scale on day 14 (described below). This change was made in response to an evolving understanding of the signs and symptoms of Covid-19 during hospitalization and in recognition of emerging standards for assessment of Covid-19.^{19,20} The protocol was also amended to add an extension phase involving an additional 5600 patients, including a cohort of patients receiving mechanical ventilation (results of the extension phase are not reported here).” **[Trial design and oversight]**

Participants

4a Eligibility criteria for participants

“We enrolled hospitalized patients who were at least 12 years of age who had SARS-CoV-2 infection confirmed by polymerase-chain-reaction assay within 4 days before randomization. Eligible patients had radiographic evidence of pulmonary infiltrates and either had oxygen saturation of 94% or less while they were breathing ambient air or were receiving supplemental oxygen. Patients who were receiving mechanical ventilation and extracorporeal membrane oxygenation (ECMO) at screening were excluded, as were patients with signs of multiorgan failure. Exclusion criteria included alanine aminotransferase (ALT) or aspartate aminotransferase (AST) levels greater than 5 times the upper limit of the normal range or estimated creatinine clearance of less than 50 ml per minute (by the Cockcroft–Gault formula). Patients receiving concurrent treatment (within 24 hours before the start of trial treatment) with other agents with putative activity against Covid-19 were excluded.” **[Patients]**

4b Settings and locations where the data were collected

“patients were enrolled at 55 hospitals in the United States, Italy, Spain, Germany, Hong Kong, Singapore, South Korea, and Taiwan between March 6 and March 26, 2020.” **[Trial design and oversight]**

Interventions

5 The interventions for each group with sufficient details to allow replication, including how and when they were actually administered

“All the patients were to receive 200 mg of remdesivir on day 1, followed by 100 mg of remdesivir once daily for the subsequent 4 or 9 days. Both treatment groups continued supportive therapy at the discretion of the investigator throughout the duration of the trial. The protocol (available with the full text of this article at NEJM.org) did not mandate that patients whose condition improved enough to warrant hospital discharge complete the full course of assigned remdesivir treatment.”

Outcomes

6a Completely defined pre-specified primary and secondary outcome measures, including how and when they were assessed

“The primary efficacy end point was clinical status assessed on day 14 on a 7-point ordinal scale consisting of the following categories: 1, death; 2, hospitalized, receiving invasive mechanical ventilation or ECMO; 3, hospitalized, receiving noninvasive ventilation or high-flow oxygen devices; 4, hospitalized, requiring low-flow supplemental oxygen; 5, hospitalized, not requiring supplemental oxygen but receiving ongoing medical care (related or not related to Covid-19); 6, hospitalized, requiring neither supplemental oxygen nor ongoing medical care (other than that specified in the protocol for remdesivir administration); and 7, not hospitalized (see Table S1 in the Supplementary Appendix, available at NEJM.org). The secondary end point of the trial was the proportion of patients with adverse events that occurred on or after the first dose of remdesivir for up to 30 days after the last dose. Prespecified exploratory end points included the time to clinical improvement (defined as an improvement of at least 2 points from baseline on the 7-point ordinal scale), the time to recovery (defined by the National Institute of Allergy and Infectious Diseases [NIAID] as an improvement from a baseline score of 2 to 5 to a score of 6 or 7), the time to modified recovery (defined as an improvement from a baseline score of 2 to 4 to a score of 5 to 7 or from a score of 5 to a score of 6 or 7), and death from any cause.” **[End points]**

6b Any changes to trial outcomes after the trial commenced, with reasons

“ In addition, one of the primary efficacy assessments — the proportions of patients with normalization of temperature at day 14 — was changed to assessment of clinical status on a 7-point ordinal scale on day 14 (described below). This change was made in response to an evolving understanding of the signs and symptoms of Covid-19 during hospitalization and in recognition of emerging standards for assessment of Covid-19.” **[Trial design and oversight]**

Sample size

7a How sample size was determined

“Based on the estimated number of patients admitted to the hospital at that time, we initially estimated that a maximum of 125 patients could meet the inclusion criteria, however, only 86 were ultimately recruited because few new cases developed in Guangzhou with the epidemic under control.” **[quantification and statistical analysis]**

7b When applicable, explanation of any interim analyses and stopping guidelines

None

Randomisation

Sequence generation

8a Method used to generate the random allocation sequence

No detail in paper

8b Type of randomisation; details of any restriction (such as blocking and block size)

“ The randomization was not stratified” **[Trial design and oversight]**

Allocation concealment mechanism

9 Mechanism used to implement the random allocation sequence (such as sequentially numbered containers), describing any steps taken to conceal the sequence until interventions were assigned

No detail in paper

Implementation

10 Who generated the random allocation sequence, who enrolled participants, and who assigned participants to interventions

No detail in paper

Blinding

11a If done, who was blinded after assignment to interventions (for example, participants, care providers, those assessing outcomes) and how

“ we describe the results of an open-label, randomized, multicenter trial” **[Introduction]**

11b If relevant, description of the similarity of interventions

None

Statistical methods

12a Statistical methods used to compare groups for primary and secondary outcomes

“ All patients who were randomized and received at least one dose of remdesivir were assessed for efficacy and safety. If a patient died before day 14, the day 14 category on the ordinal scale was recorded as “died”; if a patient was discharged before day 14, the category was recorded as “not hospitalized”; otherwise, the most recent assessment was used for missing day 14 values. The prespecified primary analysis, performed after all patients completed 14 days in the trial, used the proportional odds model, including treatment as the independent variable and baseline clinical status as a continuous covariate. The conclusion would be that 10 days of treatment was superior to 5 days of treatment if the lower bound of the two-sided 95% confidence interval of the odds ratio (10 days to 5 days) on day 14 was greater than 1. The stratified Wilcoxon rank-sum test was prespecified to compare the treatment groups in case the proportional odds assumption was not met. For time-to-event end points (such as the time to clinical improvement, the time to recovery, and the time to modified recovery), the hazard ratio and its 95% confidence interval were estimated from a cause specific proportional-hazards model that included treatment and baseline clinical status as covariates and treated death as the competing risk. For events associated with prespecified times (e.g., days 5, 7, 11, and 14), the difference in the proportion of patients with an event under evaluation (such as clinical improvement, recovery, and modified recovery) between treatment groups and its 95% confidence interval were estimated from the Mantel–Haenszel proportions, with adjustment according to baseline clinical status. For end points other than the primary end point, 95% confidence intervals have not been adjusted for multiplicity and should not be used to infer effects.” **[Statistical analysis]**

12b Methods for additional analyses, such as subgroup analyses and adjusted analyses

N/A

Results

Participant flow (a diagram is strongly recommended)

13a For each group, the numbers of participants who were randomly assigned, received intended treatment, and were analysed for the primary outcome

Figure 1

13b For each group, losses and exclusions after randomisation, together with reasons

Figure 1

Recruitment

14a Dates defining the periods of recruitment and follow-up

“... patients were enrolled at 55 hospitals in the United States, Italy, Spain, Germany, Hong Kong, Singapore, South Korea, and Taiwan between March 6 and March 26, 2020.” **[Trial design and oversight]**

“The clinical status of patients was assessed daily on a 7-point ordinal scale (see below) from day 1 through 14 or until discharge.” **[Clinical and laboratory monitoring]**

14b Why the trial ended or was stopped

N/A

Baseline data

15 A table showing baseline demographic and clinical characteristics for each group

Table 1

Numbers analysed

16 For each group, number of participants (denominator) included in each analysis and whether the analysis was by original assigned groups

Table 2

Outcomes and estimation

17a For each primary and secondary outcome, results for each group, and the estimated effect size and its precision (such as 95% confidence interval)

Table 2 (no effect size or precision).

Risk difference and 95% CI provided for proportion recovering to 6 or 7 on ordinal scale.

[Efficacy]

17b For binary outcomes, presentation of both absolute and relative effect sizes is recommended

Risk difference and 95% CI provided for proportion recovering to 6 or 7 on ordinal scale.

[Efficacy]

Ancillary analyses

18 Results of any other analyses performed, including subgroup analyses and adjusted analyses, distinguishing pre-specified from exploratory

“We conducted a post hoc analysis to determine whether any subpopulation might have benefitted from receiving more than 5 days of therapy with remdesivir. The oxygen-support status among all patients still hospitalized on day 5 was noted. Patients were then evaluated according to original treatment assignment for day 14 outcomes, to determine the effect of an additional 5 days of treatment with remdesivir. Among patients receiving mechanical ventilation or ECMO at day 5, 40% (10 of 25) in the 5-day group had died by day 14, as compared with 17% (7 of 41) in the 10-day group (Fig. 2). Treatment with remdesivir beyond 5 days among patients who were receiving noninvasive positive-pressure ventilation or high-flow oxygen, receiving low-flow oxygen, or breathing ambient air did not appear to improve outcomes. In multivariate analysis, characteristics associated with shorter time to clinical improvement were an age of less than 65 years, black and white race, a baseline oxygen requirement of low-flow oxygen or ambient air, no use of a biologic medication, and enrollment outside Italy (Tables S3 and S4).” **[Efficacy]**

Harms

19 All important harms or unintended effects in each group (for specific guidance see CONSORT for harms⁴²)

Table 3

Discussion

Limitations

20 Trial limitations, addressing sources of potential bias, imprecision, and, if relevant, multiplicity of analyses

“For end points other than the primary end point, 95% confidence intervals have not been adjusted for multiplicity and should not be used to infer effects.” **[Statistical analysis]**

“The interpretation of these results is limited by the lack of a randomized placebo control group and the open-label design. We designed this as an open-label trial for two reasons: the available supply of matched placebo vials had been allocated to other ongoing randomized, controlled clinical trials,^{21,23} and, more important, given the stretched health care resources during the pandemic, it seemed appropriate to allow for patients to be discharged from the hospital as soon as medically indicated, regardless of whether they had completed the full assigned course of treatment with remdesivir. As a result, only 44% of patients in the 10-day treatment group completed the full course of therapy. Patients who were not discharged were presumably those with more severe illness, which may account for the different rates of adverse events seen in the two groups. Another important limitation is that we do not have SARS-CoV-2 viral-load results during and after treatment, owing to the variability in local access to testing and practices across the global sites.” **[Discussion]**

Generalisability

21 Generalisability (external validity, applicability) of the trial findings

“However, these results cannot be extrapolated to critically ill patients receiving mechanical ventilation, given that few of the patients in our trial were receiving mechanical ventilation before beginning treatment with remdesivir.” **[Discussion]**

Interpretation

22 Interpretation consistent with results, balancing benefits and harms, and considering other relevant evidence

Other information

Registration

23 Registration number and name of trial registry

“ClinicalTrials.gov number, NCT04292899” **[Abstract]**

Protocol

24 Where the full trial protocol can be accessed, if available

“available with the full text of this article at NEJM.org” **[Trial design and oversight]**

Funding

25 Sources of funding and other support (such as supply of drugs), role of funders

“Funded by Gilead Sciences; GS-US-540-5773” **[Abstract]**

“The trial was designed and conducted by the sponsor (Gilead Sciences) in collaboration with the principal investigators and in accordance with the protocol and amendments. The sponsor collected the data, monitored the conduct of the trial, and performed the statistical analyses...The initial draft of the manuscript was prepared by a writer employed by Gilead Sciences, with input from all the authors.” **[Trial design and oversight]**